

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

**Analysis of historical precipitation extremes in downscaled ERA5
RCM output from Polar CORDEX**

Milestone MS30

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Milestone report

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Table of contents

1. Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone.....	4
2. Work performed and main achievements	4

1. Means of verification of the achievement of the milestone

The analysis is made available to OCEAN:ICE partners on the ftp server of partner ETT. Please note that the data will be archived in an open repository (Zenodo) for long-term access when publications in preparation are published.

2. Work performed and main achievements

NASC prepared a data archive of ERA-5 reanalysis to assess the changes in historical extreme precipitation distribution for the periods 1961-1990, 1991-2020, and 2000-2020.

The data were collected for the HCLIM43_ALADIN model over the Antarctic Region for the period 2000-2020 to develop an algorithm for the following comparison of ERA-5 data with the Horizon 2020 project [PolarRES](#) downscaled climate models output for Antarctica for the period 2000-2020.

We calculated the values per period and their changes for the first climatic index, namely the simple daily intensity index (SDII), based on the ERA-5 reanalysis and the HCLIM43_ALADIN model data.

Figure 1 below presents the calculated simple daily intensity index for Antarctica (A, B, C) and the Antarctic Peninsula region (D, E, F) for 2000-2020 based on ERA-5 data reanalysis (A, D) and the HCLIM43_ALADIN model data (B, E). The difference in the SDII value between ERA-5 data reanalysis and HCLIM43_ALADIN model data is presented in Figures 1 C. and F.

Figure 1.

